

EFFECTS OF CARBON NANOTUBE CONTENTS ON MECHANICAL AND ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES OF MULTISCALE CARBON NANOTUBE-FIBER REINFORCED EPOXY RESIN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, T700 carbon fiber (CF) reinforced epoxy composites with amino-functionalized multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT-NH₂) or with MWCNTs Bucky paper (BP) were fabricated, respectively. Unidirectional CF prepreg layers with epoxy resin modified by CNTs, were manufactured by filament winding process. Then such layers were laid up into a flat mould to fabricate the CNTs/CF/epoxy composites. BP/CF/epoxy composites were fabricated by laying up the CF prepreg layers with neat epoxy resin and the BP interleaves intercalated each of them. Both mechanical and electrical properties of carbon nanotube-fiber reinforced epoxy matrix composites were investigated with respect to contents of the CNTs. Results show that compared with the CF/epoxy composite, interlaminar shear strength of the CNTs/CF/epoxy composite with CNTs of 1.5 wt% were increased by 7.3 %. Meanwhile the longitudinal and transverse electrical conductivities of the CNTs/CF/epoxy composite with CNTs of 2.0 wt% were increased by five and ten times, respectively. Mechanical and electrical conductivities of BP/CF/epoxy composites increased significantly. Especially, the transverse electrical conductivity of BP/CF/epoxy composites was increased by two orders of magnitude approximately.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites (CFRP) are used increasingly in aerospace, automotive, sports industries and many other fields, for their high performance in mechanical properties. Beside their load bearing advantages, CFRP composites have been applied in the fields such as damage and structural health monitoring of composite materials^[1], because of their electrical conductivity. However, compared to conductive metals, the conductivity of the polymer composites reinforced with carbon fibers is far low. And, the weak electrical and mechanical properties of insulated resin matrix lead to low performance in interlaminar mechanical and transverse electrical properties. Thus, the electrical conductivity of CFRP composites, especially along the transverse direction, makes it hard to extend applications in the fields such as electromagnetic shielding. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) possess excellent electrical and mechanical properties that have potential to be used as electrical and structural materials. The incorporation of CNTs is a proper technique to improve the properties of the polymer matrix, which might enhance interlaminar mechanical properties and transverse electrical conductivity of CFRP composites at the same time^[2, 3].

CNTs consisting of one or more single graphite plane (so-called graphene) rolled up into a cylinder, possess excellent mechanical and electrical properties, especially for MWCNTs with an electrical conductivity of 1.85×10^3 S/cm^[4]. Therefore, both mechanical and electrical properties of the polymer matrix might be enhanced together, with the incorporation of CNTs. Due to the high aspect ratio and specific surface areas of CNTs, a three-dimensional conductive network could be formed in the polymer matrix at a relatively low CNT content^[5, 6]. Though the electrical conductivity of an epoxy reinforced by 2.0 vol% CNTs increased up to 10⁰ S/m approximately, it was still far low^[7]. Therefore, the epoxy resin reinforced by CNTs of high loading (10 vol%) was manufactured, and the electrical

conductivity of the composites increased up to 10^5 S/m^[8]. The results indicated that high loading of CNTs could improve the electrical conductivity of the resin matrix significantly, which have the potential to enhance the transverse electrical conductivity of CFRP composites effectively.

At the same time, uniform and steady dispersion of CNTs must be guaranteed to transfer their unique and outstanding properties to composites^[9]. Both physical and chemical methods have been applied to promote the dispersion of CNTs in the resin, including ultrasonication, high speed shear mixing, CNT surface functionalization and surfactant modification^[10]. With a proper way to disperse CNTs in the resin, the incorporation of CNTs in CFRP composites made a significant increase in the mechanical properties, including flexural strength and modulus, fracture toughness and interfacial shearing strength^[11-13]. CNTs are also expected to improve electrical properties of multiscale nanocomposites containing traditional long fibers and nanofillers^[14, 15]. Bekyarova et al. demonstrated a significant improvement of in-plane electrical conductivity and interlaminar shear strength of CFRP composites with CNTs on carbon fiber surfaces by the method of electrophoretic depositing^[16]. Hei et al. achieved an increase as high as six times for the transverse electrical conductivity of CFRP composites with 3.0 wt% CNTs^[17].

However, because of their large aspect ratio and chemical inertia, CNTs are easy to form large CNT bundles, resulting in low CNT contents in the matrix. And the high viscosity of CNT/epoxy matrix increased the difficulty of manufacturing composites. Buckypaper is a macroscopic form of preformed CNT network or mat with homogeneous dispersion and high loading. Khan et al. fabricated the CFRP composites with buckypaper made of carbon nanofibers, acquired 31 % and 104 % improvements in the interlaminar shear strength and fracture toughness^[18]. With promising electrical conductivity and mechanical performance, buckypaper demonstrated the potential to enhance the electrical and mechanical properties of CFRP composites due to higher CNTs contents. Besides, CFRP cooperated with buckypaper interleaves avoided manufacturing problems caused by the high viscosity.

This paper focuses on enhancing the transverse electrical conductivity of the unidirectional CFRP composites through adding CNTs. Influence of CNT contents on longitudinal and transverse electrical properties was studied to develop the enhancement mechanism of CNTs to CFRP composites. However, due to their large aspect ratio and high specific surface energy, it is hard for CNTs to form uniform dispersion in polymer, such as epoxy resin. Adequate CNT loading and proper dispersion technique are important for transferring CNT unique properties to composites effectively. CFRP composites reinforced with different contents of CNTs were fabricated to investigate the interlaminar mechanical and electrical properties of the composites. At relatively low loading, CNTs were dispersed in the epoxy resin directly by ultrasonication, high speed shear mixing and surfactant modification. In order to achieve higher contents of CNTs in the composites, BP/CF/epoxy composites were fabricated by inserting buckypaper interleaves between carbon fiber prepreg plies.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The matrix system used in this work consists of a diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A type epoxy (E-51, China Petrochemical Co., Balin) and an aromatic amine hardener (4, 4'-Diaminodiphenylmethane, SSS Reagents Co., Shanghai). The composites were co-reinforced by T700 carbon fiber (CF, Toray Industries Co., Japan), and amino-functionalized multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs-NH₂, Institute of Organic Chemistry, Chengdu) or buckypaper made of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (BP, Jiedi Nanotechnology Co., Suzhou). Main characteristics of the present CNTs consist of the aspect ratio (range from 1×10^3 to 1×10^4), their purity of carbon atoms (above 95 wt%), average specific surface area (233 g/m²), and electrical conductivity (above 100 S/cm). And weight percentage of the amino groups in MWCNTs-NH₂ was 0.45 wt% approximately. In order to achieve better dispersion of CNTs in the epoxy resin, Sodium Dodecyl Benzene Sulfonate (SDS, Bodi Chemical Co., Tianjin) was added at a concentration of 0.5 g/L as ionic surfactants. Characteristics of buckypaper consist of the electrical conductivity (0.8×10^5 to 7×10^5 S/m), thickness (10 to 30 μ m) and density (0.4 to 0.6 g/cm³).

2.2 Perparation of the CNTs/epoxy mixture

To manufacture the CFRP reinforced by CNTs, a CNT/epoxy suspension was first prepared. The as-prepared CNTs, added with SDS, were dispersed in acetone at 45°C. Firstly, the mixture above was dispersed by a high speed shear instrument for 15 min at the speed of 12000 r/min. Then, the mixture was sonicated for 30 min further. Such CNT suspension was blended with epoxy resin, and the mixture was dispersed by a strong sonication for another 2 hours. After the dispersion process of CNTs in the resin, the aromatic amine hardener was added at a weight percentage of 27 wt%.

2.3 Processing of unidirectional CFRP laminates with CNTs

With the epoxy resin modified by CNTs as matrix system, unidirectional CFRP prepreg layers were manufactured by filament winding process. The contents of CNTs ranging from 0.5 wt% up to 2.0 wt% were dispersed firstly in the epoxy as described above. Then ten such prepreg layers [0]₁₀ were laid up into a flat mould to fabricate the CNTs/CF/epoxy composite laminates. Buckypaper/CF/epoxy composite laminates were fabricated by laying up six neat CFRP prepreg layers [0]₆ with five buckypaper interleaves intercalated between them (as shown in Fig. 1). The composite laminates, with or without CNTs, were finally cured in a hot press mould at 95°C for 1 h, 135°C for 2 h and 170°C for 2 h, at pressure of 1.0 MPa.

Figure 1: Cross section of the buckypaper-CF reinforced composites.

2.4 Mechanical testing

The interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of the composite laminates was measured according to GB 3357-82 by short beam shear tests (SBS), with a universal mechanical testing machine at a loading speed of 0.5 mm/min. No less than ten specimens with the dimensions of 3.5 mm ×6.5 mm ×28 mm were tested for each kind of composites. After SBS tests, fracture surfaces of specimens were examined by a field emission scanning electron microscope (SEM, Hitachi S-4800) at a voltage of 5.0 KV.

2.5 Electrical conductivity measurements

Measurement of bulk electrical conductivity of the CFRP composite laminates was undertaken according to QJ 3074-98 by a resistance meter (SB-2231) from Shanghai Sixth Meter Corporation. The sample dimensions were 230 mm×15 mm×3.5 mm, whose both sides were painted with conductive silver paint to reduce the influence of contact resistance during the measurement. Each sample was drilled with four holes of 5 mm diameter, inserted with copper electrodes.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Interlaminar shear strength of the composite laminates

Fig. 2 shows the ILSS of CFRP composites changed with different CNT contents. ILSS of the composites was increased by the incorporation of both CNTs and buckypaper interleaves. Compared with neat CFRP, there was an enhancement of 7.3 % in ILSS for the composites with 1.5 wt% CNTs. Especially, when the CFRP composites inserted with buckypaper interleaves, ILSS of the composites with 5.49 wt% CNTs achieved an improvement of 45.5 %.

To understand the reinforcing mechanism of CNT contents to the ILSS, fracture surfaces of the specimens were characterized by SEM. As shown in Fig. 3, large bundles of CNTs were found in the

composites with 2.0 wt% CNTs. The agglomeration of CNTs might be the main reason for the degradation of ILSS of the composites with 2.0 wt% CNTs. Therefore, high loading of CNTs dispersed into the resin directly would decrease the mechanical properties of CFRP composites significantly because of agglomeration of the CNTs. An proper way to manufacture the composites with high loading CNTs is that inserting buckypaper into plies of CFRP composites. As could be seen in Fig. 4, the BP/CF/epoxy composites achieved a more uniform dispersion in the interleave lays without CNT agglomeration, compared to dispersing CNTs in the resin matrix directly. Above all, a CNT content of 5.49 wt% was incorporated in the composites, avoiding manufacturing problems caused by the high viscosity. Besides, more roughness morphology can be observed on the fracture surface of BP/CF/epoxy composites.

Figure 2: The ILSS of CFRP composites with CNTs.

Figure 3: SEM micrographs of the fracture surfaces of SBS test specimens with 2.0 wt% CNTs dispersed in the resin.

Figure 4: SEM micrographs of the fracture surfaces of SBS test specimens with BP interleaves.

3.2 Electrical conductivity

The longitudinal and transverse electrical conductivity were measured by a DC resistance meter for the CFRP composites with CNTs or buckypaper interleaves. Compared to the composites reinforced

with carbon fiber alone, an improvement was achieved both in the longitudinal and transverse electrical conductivity. As shown in Fig. 5, an improvement was achieved for the composites with CNTs of 2.0 wt%, as high as five and ten times for the longitudinal and transverse electrical conductivities respectively.

Compared to the composites with 1.5 wt% CNTs, an increase in the electrical conductivity of the composites with 2.0 wt% CNTs was acquired, while a decrease in the mechanical property. A proper reason for the above phenomenon is that the large CNT bundles play different roles between the electrical and mechanical properties. On one hand, the CNT bundles may induce defects in the composites, resulting the degradation of mechanical properties. On the other hand, the CNT bundles caused nonuniform spots of electrical conductivity merely. Hence, it means that the electron conduct channels could be strengthened further with CNTs at higher loading. However, the viscosity of resin rised rapidly with increasing CNT contents, which made it difficulty to fabricate the composites. Therefore, CNTs in the form of buckypaper were incorporated into the composites with 5.49 wt% CNTs. As predicted, the electrical conductivity was significantly improved by the relatively higher CNT contents. Experimental results showed that the longitudinal conductivity of BP/CF/epoxy composites was increased by ten times, and meanwhile the transverse electrical conductivity was enhanced by two orders of magnitude approximately.

Figure 5: The electrical conductivity of CFRP with CNTs along the longitudinal (a) and transverse (b) directions.

The electrical conductivity of CFRP was related closely with material conductivity and the contact numbers. The incorporation of CNTs contributed to form three dimensional conductive networks in two main approaches: one is increasing the contact numbers between CNTs; another is increasing the contact numbers between carbon fibers through CNT bridging (as shown in Fig. 6). Therefore, the increased conductivity of CFRP could be attributed to the contact numbers improved by adding CNTs, validated by the results of SEM micrographs (as seen in Fig. 4).

Based on previous studies, the electrical conductivity of polymers could gain several orders of magnitude when the CNT content was above the percolation threshold. However, as CFRP is not insulative, the percolation phenomena is not expected to be observed with the incorporation of CNTs. Nevertheless, this paper demonstrates that the incorporation of CNTs generated a significant increase in the transverse electrical conductivity of CFRP by improving the contact numbers effectly, to form more electron transport channels. Therefore, the electrical conductivity of composites acquired a noticeable improvement by adding 2.0 wt% CNTs. Especially, when the CNT loading was up to 5.49 wt% in the form of buckypaper interleaves, the electrical conductivity was enhanced remarkably. The significant enhancement might be due to the higher content of CNTs in the composites, and more importantly, the uniform CNTs are benefit for forming dense networks, which can transfer the stress and current more effectively.

Figure 6: The sketch map of enhancement mechanism for electrical conductivity.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The present study demonstrated the effective enhancement in the electrical conductivity along longitudinal and transverse directions of CFRP composite laminates with the CNTs or buckypaper interleaves, without compromising the mechanical properties. The CFRP composites with CNTs or buckypaper, were fabricated to investigate the effect of CNT contents on the mechanical and electrical properties of the composites.

As to the mechanical properties, the ILSS of the composites was enhanced with the incorporation of CNTs. By dispersing CNTs directly into the epoxy resin, the ILSS of CNTs/CF/epoxy composites containing 1.5 wt% CNTs was increased by 7.3 %. When the CNT contents rised up to 5.49 wt% in the form of buckypaper, the ILSS of the composites was significantly improved by 45.5 %. Regarding to the electrical properties, the longitudinal and transverse electrical conductivity of CFRP were enhanced by the incorporation of CNTs, with the improvement as high as five and ten times, respectively for the composites with 2.0 wt% CNTs. Likewise, the electrical conductivity of composites with 5.49 wt% CNTs was significantly increased. Especially, the transverse electrical conductivity of BP/CF/epoxy composites was increased by two orders of magnitude approximately. In summary, the results demonstrated a proper approach to increase significantly both mechanical and electrical properties of CFRP with high loading of CNTs, broading the applied fields for the composites. What is more, the method of incorporating CNTs in the form of buckypaper interleaves could be applied to fabricate the composites with high CNT loadings and without large CNT bundles.

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